

In Vitro Assessment of Pakistani Bee Propolis Extract Against *Staphylococcus Aureus*

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Abstract

Antibiotic resistance of *Staphylococcal* infections has prompted the pharmaceutical and scientific community to consider alternate treatments. Propolis is a natural substance produced by honey bees from the exudates of different plants. The aim of the current study was to evaluate the antibacterial activity of ethanolic extracts of Pakistani bee propolis against *Staphylococcus aureus*. The Propolis sample was collected from district Kohat and dried in the dark until processed. The dried propolis was dissolved in ethanol solvent and concentrated by evaporating the solvent through a rotary vacuum evaporator to obtain the final extract. The antibacterial activity of propolis extract was examined using the Agar well diffusion method. *Staphylococcus aureus* culture was incubated on MHA media. Five different concentration of propolis, 100 µg/ml, 200 µg/ml, 350 µg/ml, 500 µg/ml and 650 µg/ml were used. Gentamicin disc was used as a positive control. After 24 hours, the antibacterial activity of propolis extracts was checked, and the zone of inhibition was measured. Experiments were performed in triplicate. The mean zone of inhibition and standard deviation for each concentration were, 17 ± 0.816 at 650 µg/ml, 14.6 ± 0.471 at 500 µg/ml, 12 ± 1.41 at 300 µg/ml, 9.6 ± 0.942 at 200 µg/ml, 2.3 ± 0.471 at 100 µg/ml of propolis extract.

It was observed that by increasing the concentration of propolis extract, the antibacterial activity also increased. The extracts showed less antibacterial potential compared to standard antibiotic disc Gentamicin. The current study found that an ethanolic extract of Pakistani bee propolis had antibacterial potential against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Further research is needed to assess the biochemical contents of Pakistani bee propolis for use as a natural antibacterial

agent in a variety of applications.

Keywords: Propolis, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *In vitro*.